

QUERCETIN-HYDROGEL THREE DIMENSIONAL SCAFFOLD TO FACILITATE REGENERATION FOLLOWING SPINAL CORD INJURY

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Abstract

Spinal cord injury (SCI) is a serious health issue with no gold standard treatment. New therapeutic strategies with neuro-regenerative and neuro-protective prosperities are required. Recently several studies have shown that the combination of cellular therapy with Gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA) hydrogel biomaterials in spinal cord injury could provide a potential solution for the regeneration of spinal cord.

Quercetin nanoparticles could provide a synergistic effect when combined with the ASCs laden 3D GelMA hydrogels to support the regeneration in SCI rat model. In this study, quercetin nanoparticles were loaded into the three-dimensional (3D) soft gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA) (5%) scaffold supplemented with adipose tissue-derived stromal cells (ASCs) and then they were implanted into the hemisection site of the rat spinal cord.

We found that ASCs that were photo-encapsulated in the 3D GelMA hydrogel loaded with 10 μmol quercetin nanoparticles demonstrated a higher proliferation rate in vitro after 7 days. Besides, quercetin nanoparticles have improved the mechanical properties of the hydrogel scaffold. Moreover, when ASCs laden quercetin-hydrogels were implanted into the hemisection site of the rat spinal cord, the hydrogel filled the gap and organized tissue was noted at the site of injury. Therefore, the ASCs laden quercetin-hydrogels is a promising therapeutic strategy to trigger functional regeneration of the spinal cord.

Graphical Abstract

Acknowledgment

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Results

Figure 1: Imaging and elastic modulus of hydrogels. (A1&B1) The strain-stress curve of the hydrogel and Quercetin hydrogel showed maximum stress points at 0.045 N/mm² and 0.059 N/mm², respectively. Mechanical compression testing revealed that both hydrogels displayed a gradual increase in stiffness and typically showed a linear stress-strain relationship up to 90% strain followed by a non-linear response. (C) Quercetin hydrogel was mechanically stronger than the hydrogel alone. (0.078 N/mm² vs. 0.062 N/mm² elastic modulus, respectively). (A2&B2) SEM images of hydrogels showing porosity of the hydrogels.

Results

Figure 2: Proliferation and angiogenic potential of the scaffold. (A) Isolated Chorioallantoic membrane (CAM), showing the angiogenic potential of the Hydrogel and Quercetin hydrogel in comparison to the Matrigel (positive control). (B) The percentage of angiogenesis induction showing a slight decrease in the Quercetin hydrogel. © Quantitative analysis of the branching point number showing a decrease in the number of branching points of Quercetin hydrogel as well. (D) 3D confocal microscope images show an increase in proliferation of ASCs encapsulated in Quercetin hydrogel indicated by viable ASCs stained with calcein AM live stain.

Figure 3: PCR of inflammatory markers of spinal cord tissues upon treatment with different methodologies.

Results

Figure 4: PCR of neural markers of the differentiated ASCs that had been implanted in the scaffold.

Figure 5: Histological sections of the scaffold after transplantation. (A,B) Hydrogel scaffold supported by ASCs with more differentiated neural cells occupied the scaffold (Black arrows) stained by H&E (A) and cresyl violet (B). (C,D) Quercetin hydrogel scaffold supported by ASCs with less differentiated neural cells occupied the scaffold (Black arrows) stained by H&E (C) and cresyl violet (D).

Conclusion and Future Direction

In conclusion, Quercetin micelles could provide a synergistic effect when combined with the ASCs laden 3D GelMA hydrogels to support the regeneration in SCI rat model and modulate the inflammatory response. Further investigations of the effect on motor function required.